

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

Dissemination and Communication Plan

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the initial plan for dissemination and communication at project level in SYNERGIES. This includes a basic communication strategy, planning of events and activities, and a clear definition of the goals for each activity (what the project wants to achieve), the target audience, addressed channels and media, involved partners, key messages, a time plan, and which indicators for success are used.

While practically each work package in SYNERGIES will have its dedicated dissemination and/or exploitation activities, there is a dedicated, central WP (WP10, Tasks T10.1 - communication and T10.2 - dissemination) defined in the project, which deals with managing and coordinating these activities project-wide. The key objectives defined for WP10 are:

- Objective 1: Building the project awareness beyond the scope of the consortium
- Objective 2: Effective dissemination of project results via multiple channels.
- Objective 3: Communicating the project results and achievements to external parties
- Objective 4: Establish standardization in project-related topics
- Objective 5: Creating and delivering valuable educational and training content

The goal is to improve the impact of the project by stimulating and optimizing dissemination and communication, as well as in aligning linked activities, and providing additional opportunities at project level (e.g. public events, press releases, conference workshops, etc.).

An important part is to optimize communication within the project. This is done by establishing and maintaining SharePoint as main communication and document management platform.

A key factor is an informative, easy-to-find project website (see D10.2); it will provide current project news to the public and allow a low-barrier introduction into project objectives, activities and partners and contacts. It will also act as repository for (public) deliverables and will be accompanied by appropriate means of social media solutions.

In addition, SYNERGIES will use multiple channels on social networks, to provide fast, low-latency updates about SYNERGIES activities.

This document serves as a reference point at project start. It will be updated at the end of the project (D10.5, due M36) to report on the activities and results, and to reflect the most current achievements of the consortium. In addition, an update on the status of the activities will be provided as part of the yearly periodic progress reports.

Keywords: Communication, dissemination, cooperation, strategy, plan, target audience, key messages

2 OBJECTIVES

2.1 Overall view on measures to maximize impact

The SYNERGIES project aims to improve the development of the CCAM technologies and their implementation towards harmonisation and standardization. To reach this, the project will collaborate with the main public and private stakeholders for alignment to ensure the project outputs' longevity and usability. During the project, the consortium will:

- **Collaborate with OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturer) and Tiers** to develop and implement solutions that cover their needs for the development of CCAM technologies to safely extend current ODDs (Operational Design Domain), increasing their usability and potential benefits.
- **Collaborate with public and private stakeholders** to access and analyse existing datasets, ensuring comprehensive insights into road safety challenges and opportunities and the alignment of the project outputs.
- **Build on experiences in projects Hi-Drive and SUNRISE** and others identified during the project duration, to align with previous work done and to provide outputs for future research projects.

SYNERGIES has foreseen two dedicated WPs (9 and 10), including a series of tasks, bodies, and roles to maximize the impact of its outcomes and to ensure that SYNERGIES Platform will be representative, scalable, usable and widely accepted and adopted by the stakeholder community. We distinguish between:

- **Communication** (WP10, T10.1), directed at the public and media, using the communication tools set up by WP10 and described in section 3.1.
- **Dissemination** (WP10, T10.2), directed at key stakeholders and users to inform about the projects aims, progress and results, regarding the developed platform, tools, and processes, detailed in section 3.2.
- **Stakeholder Engagement** (WP9, T9.1-T9.3), directed at the wide community concerned by Autonomous Vehicle (AV) development and safety assessment (research, industry, type approval, consumer testing, standardization). A harmonized solution that reflects and addresses the needs of the concerned community requires, beyond the dissemination of project results, continuous engagement of the stakeholders in all stages of the project. WP9 will put at the disposal of all WPs the required tools (workshops and online cooperation platform) and liaise with other international initiatives.
- **Exploitation** (WP1, T1.3), directed at commercial, societal, and policymaking organisations and institutions. This task will monitor market needs, policy and regulatory developments and technical evolutions maximising the exploitation of the project (final outcomes) in concertation with all SYNERGIES partners and external stakeholders.
- **Standardization** (WP9, WP10, T10.3): To comprehensively address urban and rural scenarios, along with longer and more complex scenarios involving multiple participants (including potential scenario concatenation), it is essential to extend and adapt existing standards (ISO, SAE, ASAM, BSI, UNECE, Euro NCAP). Leveraging the partners' representation in standardization bodies, proposals will be presented for discussion (WP9) to maximize project impact. Implementation of standardization actions

will take place in T10.3. The results will be reported in the periodic progress report and deliverable D10.3 (M36).

- **Data Interoperability:** Aligned with the European Data Strategy, SYNERGIES will develop a federated approach in forming a European Scenario Dataspace (WP6) enhancing the versatility and accessibility of scenarios available for safety validation. The Open Connectors will facilitate seamless interconnection of individual databases within the framework, ensuring scenario ownership sovereignty and offering comprehensive access control through individual contracts and access management. This strategy establishes a secure framework for stakeholders to collaboratively share updated scenarios, accident data, findings, etc., in pursuit of European safety validation.
- **Education and Training** (WP10, T10.4) directed at end users. Training sessions, accompanied by the dedicated documentation will facilitate the adoption of the SYNERGIES Platform and the onboarding of new users. The results will be reported in the periodic progress report and deliverable D10.4 (M36).

Figure 1 shows the positioning of WP10 in context of the other SYNERGIES work packages.

Figure 1 Positioning of WP10

2.2 Objectives related to communication and dissemination

In the following, the overall objectives of WP10 are listed. For this deliverable, objectives 1-3 are most relevant. Objectives 4 and 5 will be covered in detail by other deliverables & the periodic progress reports, but of course are still relevant for the daily work in WP10.

- **Objective 1: Building the project awareness beyond the scope of the consortium**
 - It is addressed in this deliverable and in D10.2. "Project website" (due M5) and updated in the final deliverable D10.5 "Final dissemination and communication plan", due in M36. In addition, an update on the status of the activities will be provided as part of the yearly periodic progress reports.
- **Objective 2: Effective dissemination of project results via multiple channels.**
 - It is addressed in this deliverable and in D10.2. "Project website" (due M5) and updated in the final deliverable D10.5 "Final dissemination and communication

plan", due in M36. In addition, an update on the status of the activities will be provided as part of the yearly periodic progress reports.

- **Objective 3: Communicating the project results and achievements to external parties**
 - It is addressed in this deliverable and in D10.2. "Project website" (due M5) and updated in the final deliverable D10.5 "Final dissemination and communication plan", due in M36. In addition, an update on the status of the activities will be provided as part of the yearly periodic progress reports.
- **Objective 4: Establish standardization in project-related topics**
 - This is being addressed in Section 0. and it will be reported in detail in D10.3 "Report on dissemination and standardization activities", due M36. In addition, an update on the status of the activities will be provided as part of the yearly periodic progress reports.
- **Objective 5: Creating and delivering valuable educational and training content**
 - This is being addressed in Section 3.4. and it will be reported in detail in D10.4 "Training material", due M36. In addition, an update on the status of the activities will be provided as part of the yearly periodic progress reports.

Overall objective:

Ensure **maximization of impact** of the project through effective **dissemination** of the project results and **communication** with external entities, **standardization** activities and **education/training**.

2.3 Key performance indicators (KPIs)

In this section, Table 1 contains an overview on the communication & dissemination KPIs.

Channel	Purpose	Target Groups	Metrics	Target
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Google search term "CCAM SYNERGIES project"	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Qwant search term "CCAM SYNERGIES project"	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Baidu search term "CCAM SYNERGIES project"	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Google search term "Scenarios for development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems"	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Qwant search term "Scenarios for development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems"	Ranked 1 st

Channel	Purpose	Target Groups	Metrics	Target
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	Ranking on Baidu search term "Scenarios for development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems"	Ranked 1 st
Website	Public information and all public deliverables, online destination for target audiences (knowledge hub)	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	#unique visitors #news postings	≥1000 views/year, ≥12 news/year
Newsletters	Project developments, results, deliverables, presentations/publications	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	#readers #newsletters	≥100 recipients /newsletter ≥2 newsletters/year
Linkedin	Draw attention to news, events, results on website	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users, standardization bodies, automotive industry, research community	#followers on Linkedin	≥250 followers by year 3 ¹
Talks, conferences and events	Disseminating findings and conducting direct conversations with target audiences	Policy makers/authorities, automotive industry, research community	#conferences #presentations	≥8 conferences/year
Press releases and articles	Project innovations and results in easily accessible magazines published	Policy makers/authorities, general public, end-users	#releases/articles	≥10 releases and/or articles

¹ While in the GA a higher KPI is defined, based on experience from previous projects this value is more realistic. Hence, we propose to use this value.

Channel	Purpose	Target Groups	Metrics	Target
Scientific publications	Dissemination of scientific project results	Automotive industry, research community	#papers and/or publications	≥20 papers
Internal collab. platform	Foster interactive collaboration, communication, and dissemination within the SYNERGIES project	Project partners	Number of SharePoint users	100
Internal collab. platform	Foster interactive collaboration, communication, and dissemination within the SYNERGIES project	Project partners	Number of SharePoint documents	500

Table 1 Key performance indicators

2.4 Audiences

The project activities, results, and deliverables shall be widely disseminated at national and European level to the following audiences:

- **Specific “external audiences”** such as relevant target groups, institutions, organizations, other projects, as well as individuals.
- **Wider “external audiences”** such as ‘the community’ or the broad public, and
- **the “internal audience”**, i.e. all partners of the SYNERGIES consortium.

More details are laid out in section 3.1.1.

3 DESCRIPTION OF WORK

3.1 Communication in SYNERGIES (T10.1)

As described in chapter 2, the most important objectives of the SYNERGIES dissemination and communication activities are:

- Building the project awareness beyond the scope of the consortium
- Effective dissemination of project results via multiple channels.
- Communicating the project results and achievements to external parties

In order to demonstrate how the project contributes to tackling societal challenges, SYNERGIES dissemination and communication is aligned with the structure defined in "Fact Sheet: The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020" [1] and other similar documents/guidelines [2],[3],[4],[5], answering following questions:

- What kind of needs does SYNERGIES project respond to?
- What kind of problems will the proposed solutions of SYNERGIES solve, and why will these solutions be better than existing ones? In which areas will they excel?
- What new knowledge (results) will SYNERGIES generate (including assessment of the state of the art)?
- Who will use these results?
- What benefits will be delivered?
- How will end users be informed about the generated results?

Our goal is to **communicate** new events (like a new publication, a public presentation, a demonstration, or a comment on a recent event) **targeted and adapted to fit for the different target groups**, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Targeted distribution adapted for specific channels

3.1.1 Definition of stakeholders and multipliers to be addressed

WP9 and WP10 serve in continuously identifying relevant stakeholders and multipliers for SYNERGIES.

The following stakeholders have been identified for dissemination and exploitation activities in project SYNERGIES:

- SYNERGIES project partners
- Other related EU (European Union) / national projects / project participants
- Industry
 - Industry & Business Associations
 - Applied researchers in industry
 - Researchers / Experts from the field of policy, science and industry
- Academia
 - Academic communities and other interest groups, of the domains addressed in SYNERGIES (railway, smart infrastructure, maritime, manufacturing, health, building, urban public transport, automotive, aeronautics);
 - Domain-specific forums and interest groups
 - Students (PhD or Master thesis)
- Policy Makers
 - Public authorities involved
 - European Union / European Commission
 - National Governments
 - Standardization organizations (industry, national, international)
- Public
 - Regional, national and international media
 - End users (citizens and professional users), general public

Important stakeholders, who can take the role of opinion makers / leaders as well as a catalyst, may serve as "**multipliers**" regarding the efficient and effective dissemination of / spreading information on activities, results and deliverables.

For SYNERGIES such **multipliers** may be in particular:

- Representatives from industry & business associations, academic communities, and other interest groups
- Researchers / experts from the field of policy, science and industry
- Other related EU projects & project participants
- High-level officials from the EU
- Public authorities involved
- Standardization organizations (industry, national, international)
- Regional, national and international media
- SYNERGIES partner consortium

To reach a broader public and share project results, SYNERGIES's communication strategy includes targeted information via several channels, see following sections. SYNERGIES partners will identify relevant stakeholders and multipliers on both regional and national level (media,

interested entities, representatives from industry and business associations) and communicate the project results among them.

3.1.2 Project website

An easy to find project website is essential to make the project known, and to disseminate results.

Our intended audience includes

- Potential customers for SYNERGIES's exploitable foreground
- Experts in industry and academia interested in using or referring to SYNERGIES results
- Research and education organisation interested in the body of knowledge resulting from SYNERGIES
- General public interested in state of the art and ongoing research of development, training, virtual testing, and validation of connected, cooperative, and automated mobility (CCAM) systems
- Governmental organisations, standard organisations, NGO etc. looking for related expertise

The **project website** (<https://synergies-ccam.eu/>) will come online in October 2024, see Deliverable D10.2 (M5) for more information.

It will provide an easy-to-read introduction to the project, its objectives, partners and means of contact. It will also inform about current (project-related) news and activities and of course act as repository for (public) deliverables.

All partners in the project are encouraged to use their own company or institute websites to link and promote the SYNERGIES project. Ideally, links to SYNERGIES project website will be made from most of the partner websites.

To fulfil its goal, the SYNERGIES website must be designed and continuously maintained with search-engine optimization (SEO) in mind.

Using the following three search engines in a private session (non-personalized) in Firefox we will periodically check and report on rankings (see Table 1 in section 2.3) for typical search strings relating to SYNERGIES.

1. <https://www.google.at/>
2. <https://www.qwant.com/>
3. <http://www.baidu.com>

3.1.3 Social networks

SYNERGIES will use social network channels (see Table 2) extensively to serve as additional (also first-time) source of information about the project.

Social Network Channel	Link	Metrics	Target
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/synergies-ccam-project/	#followers ²	≥250 followers by year 3

Table 2 Social network channels and performance indicators in SYNERGIES

3.1.4 Newsletters

Project news will be circulated through the project platforms and consortium partners' channels. In addition, SYNERGIES will give the members of the project SUNRISE (Safety Assurance Framework For Connected And Automated Mobility Systems) Expert Platform (<https://ccam-sunrise-project.eu/tools/expert-platform/>) the possibility to subscribe to the SYNERGIES newsletter. Interaction with stakeholders will also serve to validate the (intermediate) results and act as guidance in the case that a steer in the activities could reduce risks and/or increase impact.

To keep the stakeholders and partners communities updated and duly informed, as well as to maximize the outreach of the project's news, an internal (consortium) newsletter and an external newsletter will be drafted. The target audience for this latter will combine the industrial and scientific community, and the general public, as outlined in Table 1.

3.1.5 Project-internal collaboration

Project SYNERGIES will use Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by IDIADA, as the project's main repository and communication platform. The screenshot in Figure 3 was taken on 2024-08-29.

² While in the GA a higher KPI is defined, based on experience from previous projects this value is more realistic. Hence, we propose to use this value.

Figure 3 Screenshot of SYNERGIES's SharePoint landing page

It includes

- Contracts (GA, PCA (Project Consortium Agreement))
- Meetings (e.g., agendas, presentations)
- Administrative material (e.g., templates)
- WP1 ... WP10 repositories (e.g., presentations, documents, deliverables)
- Deliverables (project-wide collection)
- Reporting documents (internal and external)
- Pictures (library)
- Events
- Communication and Dissemination activities

The usage of the SharePoint will be measured using two KPIs:

- Number of users (target: 100)
- Number of documents (target: 500)

3.1.6 Communication materials

In terms of marketing and communication materials, the project strategy is to remain as paperless as possible, except for the roll-up banner, which could be reused throughout the project at events organised by the project as well as external events, and leaflets to present at in-person events to inform the attendees about the project's main facts and figures.

We will propose a stock of selected relevant images and pictures to be used in the different communication activities (e.g., articles, banners, social media posts).

Different communication templates will be produced and distributed. These shall be updated or re-styled twice per year, if deemed necessary. The visual identity should not, nevertheless, differ excessively from the initial templates to maintain the project's branding features.

Microsoft Word and PowerPoint templates with SYNERGIES branding have been updated for the partners to use for dissemination and communication purposes, including for presentations and project's submissions. This will allow to create a unique and efficient communication branding.

Figure 4 Communication materials

3.1.7 Communication events

The SYNERGIES final event (to be held in IDIADA facilities around the last months of the project) will focus on the impact and the way forward for the exploitation and sustainability of the project's work.

In addition, SYNERGIES members will attend various public events to present and demonstrate the vision and outcomes of the project. You can find a list of events that have been identified by SYNERGIES partners as the most relevant and important conferences/events to be targeted in a follow-up section (3.2.5.2 Key Conferences and Events for SYNERGIES).

3.1.8 Key messages

The following key message was defined in the proposal: "Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems".

An extended version of it is:

The SYNERGIES Key Message

SYNERGIES Platform features an inclusive framework providing scenarios for the development, training, virtual testing, and validation of CCAM systems:

- (i) Designed to be sustainable: Dynamic with regular updates, allowing new data sources and new data collection;**
- (ii) For all scenarios: motorways, urban and rural;**
- (iii) Including everything from: accident data to real driving data;**
- (iv) Implementing AI-enabled data processing tools and scenario variation tools and;**
- (v) Usable by all concerned stakeholders.**

3.1.9 Elevator pitch

During the first year of SYNERGIES, an elevator pitch will be created. An elevator pitch is a brief, persuasive speech used to spark interest in a person, product, idea, or business. It typically lasts 30 to 60 seconds—about the length of an elevator ride—hence the name. The goal is to convey the most essential and compelling points in a clear, concise way, so that the listener is intrigued and wants to learn more.

Key components of the elevator pitch will be:

- Introduction: Who we are or what we are offering.
- Value proposition: What problem we are solving and why it matters.
- Call to action: What we want the listener to do next (e.g., schedule a meeting, visit a website).

It's useful in networking events, interviews, or sales scenarios.

3.2 Dissemination in SYNERGIES (T10.2)

3.2.1 Introduction

It is the SYNERGIES dissemination plan that accounts for ensuring the long-term impact and exploitation of the products of the project. This document presents of the dissemination approaches which are all geared at improving the visibility, extent, and engagement of the key stakeholders. Besides, while raising awareness is one of those specific impacts, there are plans to link dissemination activities with the much wider and broader objectives of standardization, stakeholder empowerment, and technology diffusion. The Dissemination procedure has been sent the partners and can be found in Annex 1.

3.2.2 Dissemination objectives and strategic approach

To guarantee that far more than just the visibility of the project deliverables is available, the overall objective of SYNERGIES' activities on dissemination is to make project deliverables accessible and actionable for the targeted target groups. The following primary goals shall be at the basis of the dissemination strategy:

1. **Build Project Awareness Beyond the Consortium:** Apart from ensuring visibility, the strategy will go a step further to help connect with key figures in industry, policy, or research able to lead in promoting utilization and embedding the technology. This includes endorsing the results of the project to appropriate and powerful change agents.
2. **Effective Dissemination of Results Through Targeted Channels:** A multi-channel dissemination approach will be deployed, without losing target's attention using different approaches to communicate. No matter what, from academic journals to industry conferences, these tools will be employed wherever possible to facilitate decision making in target stakeholders.
3. **Communicating Achievements to External Stakeholders:** Additional responsibilities should devise a way of informing the stakeholders as well as promoting a participatory approach on the project results. There will be active marketing as well as adoption of communication activities with a view of building relations with standardization organizations, businesses, and government with the aim of increasing acceptance of new ideas and concepts.
4. **Improving the Practice of Standards and Norms:** Among the system elements of SYNERGIES is its capacity to contribute in the further development of standards on connected cooperative and automated mobility (CCAM). The dissemination will focus on certain key standardization organisations, providing evidence based materials, preventing policymakers from working on regulatory frameworks of the future which may not be required.
5. **Supplying of Educational and Training Materials:** It is clear that education is necessary in order for the project's technologies to reach a level of adoption which could be sustained. The strategy also suggests the provision of such training materials as would meet the precise requirements of the practitioners in the industry, as well as the researchers and the policymakers.

3.2.3 Dissemination means and channels

The dissemination means must be chosen not just for visibility, but for their ability to catalyse action and influence decision-making. A detailed analysis of communication channels reveals the most effective dissemination tactics for each target audience. T10.2 Leader (ICCS) has drafted detailed dissemination procedures where it is described, step-by-step, what actions need to be done to ensure proper and coherent dissemination as well as to track the activities on the time that is derived by the GA (Grant Agreement) and the CA (Consortium Agreement) (see appendix A). Moreover, in the same framework a dissemination activity report has been prepared and uploaded to SharePoint, alongside with the Dissemination Procedures, to help the partners to describe and report the activities that they are going to participate (See appendix B).

3.2.3.1 Scientific publications

Hitting the targeted statistical high-value peer review research journal is critical in terms of having status within the scientist community. There is a need to go beyond just presenting the conclusions and even the implications of the research and move to predicting the current and future developments of the research field. Expected publications will be directed towards high-value value-citation indexed journals including but not limited to IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, Computer Networks, Elseviers and other academic journals.

3.2.3.2 Conferences and events

Participation in key conferences (ITS World Congress, IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, etc) provides opportunities for real-time dialogue with global leaders in mobility innovation. The strategic selection of events based on attendee demographics ensures that resources are

invested where they yield the highest return in terms of industry and policy influence. This tactic is particularly useful for aligning project outcomes with industry standards and public policy frameworks.

3.2.3.3 Website and social media

The project website will function as a knowledge hub, offering open access to results and tools for stakeholders. Beyond information dissemination, web analytics will be utilized to measure engagement, track geographical reach, and assess which stakeholders are interacting with the materials. Social media engagement will be monitored through LinkedIn for its professional networking capabilities, targeting thought leaders and industry influencers.

3.2.3.4 Workshops and webinars

In addition to providing dissemination, workshops serve as a feedback loop from stakeholders. A key analytical metric will be the depth and quality of engagement, assessed through post-workshop surveys and feedback forms, which can directly inform project improvements and adaptive strategies. Moreover, these engagements will be a conduit for integrating stakeholder input into subsequent project iterations.

3.2.3.5 Educational and training materials

The creation of educational content is intended to foster a deep understanding of CCAM systems. This aspect of dissemination is critical for building a workforce skilled in the application of SYNERGIES technologies, thereby ensuring long-term adoption. A robust partnership with educational institutions will be pivotal for maximizing the reach and relevance of the training materials. A summer school will be implemented building on the experience gained by HI-DRIVE.

3.2.4 Target audience and key messages

Target Audience	Key Message	Approach
OEMs and Tier 1 Suppliers	Insights demonstrating clear ROI (Return of Investment) and competitive advantage gained from adopting SYNERGIES technologies.	Dissemination efforts will be focused on participation in advisory boards and high-level industry events, where decision-makers are present.
Research Community	Novelty of the project's approach and its contribution to advancing CCAM technology, focusing on fostering innovation.	Engaged through high-quality scientific publications, targeting top-tier journals, and collaborating in follow-up research initiatives. Success is measured by the number of citations and subsequent research collaborations.
Policymakers and Public Authorities	How SYNERGIES contributes to safer, more efficient mobility systems that align with regulatory goals and policy frameworks.	Messaging tailored for participation in policy roundtables, direct liaisons, and the creation of detailed reports showcasing the project's contributions to regulatory frameworks and public safety improvements.

Target Audience	Key Message	Approach
End-Users and the General Public	Simplified messages focused on the societal benefits of SYNERGIES, such as improved road safety, reduced emissions, and real-world applications of mobility innovations.	Information will be disseminated through popular science articles, news platforms, and general interest media to create broad awareness of the project's benefits, with the aim of engaging the public and demonstrating real-world impact.

Table 3 Target audience and key messages

3.2.5 Dissemination plan and activities

3.2.5.1 Conferences, events and publications

Using its participation in conferences, workshops, and exhibitions SYNERGIES will combine for the project visibility and report to targets through personal interaction. The goal is also to communicate the results of the project, receive feedback and make contacts with potential users of the technology. In this way, SYNERGIES hopes to change the standards and policies of the industry, as well as encourage the use of connected and automated mobility (CCAM) technologies.

3.2.5.2 Key Conferences and events for synergies

From the Individual Dissemination plans, SYNERGIES has been able to identify some critical events for dissemination. These indicative events are aimed at key category of people who include business executives, decision makers, researchers and users of the technology.

Event No.	Name of Event	Date	Place	Presenting Partner(s)	What to Present
1	Transport Research Board Automated Road Transportation Symposium (TRB ARTS)	29/7/24	San Diego, USA	IDIADA	Panel discussion + Plenary (SYNERGIES introduction) - Done
2	IAA Transportation 2024	Sep 17-22, 2024	Hanover, Germany	IVEX	Project participation;
3	CENEX Expo	Sep 4-5, 2024	Bedford, UK	ERTICO, IDIADA	Project status and future impact on CCAM industry
4	ITS World Congress	Sep 16-20, 2024	Dubai, UAE	ERTICO	Introduction to SYNERGIES project and goals
5	GSVF 2024	26.9.2024	Graz	VIF	Networking with partners about the project & results.
6	SUNRISE General Assembly	Oct 1-2, 2024	San Sebastián, Spain	ERTICO	Exploitation Workshop

7	33. Aachen Colloquium Sustainable Mobility	Oct 7-9, 2024	Aachen, Germany	RWTH (IKA)	Generation and usage of scenarios within safety assessment and assurance of automated driving
8	Mobility Innovation Week Japan 2024	Nov 14, 2024	Nagoya, Japan	DLR	Basic SYNERGIES architecture, networking with international partners
9	ASAM International Conference	Dec 04-05, 2024	Munich, Germany	BMW, IVEX	ASAM OSI trace files for sensor data collection and OS project for their visualization - Project participation
10	CES	Jan 7-10, 2025	Las Vegas, USA	IVEX	Project Content
11	Global Symposium on Mobility Innovation	March 18-19, 2025	Michigan, USA	ERTICO	TBC
12	VECS	March 18-19, 2025	Gothenburg, Sweden	IVEX	Project participation
13	EUCAD Symposium	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Ispra, Italy (2025)	CLEPA, ERTICO, IDIADA, ICCS, MOSAIC FACTOR SL	Main project results
14	AVS (Automated Vehicle Symposium – Europe)	May 20-22, 2025	Stuttgart, Germany	ERTICO, IVEX, REN	TBC
15	ITS European Congress	June 2-4, 2025	Sevilla, Spain	ERTICO, ICCS, PAVE	Project presentation
16	World Mobility Conference	June 3-5, 2025	Barcelona, Spain	ERTICO	TBC
17	IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium	June 22-25, 2025	Napoca, Romania	ERTICO, RWTH (IKA), ICCS	Present scientific papers on CCAM innovations
18	IAA Conference	Sep 9-14, 2025	Munich, Germany	ERTICO	TBC
19	SAFER Seminar Series	2025 (Date TBD)	Gothenburg, Sweden	RISE	SYNERGIES overview and early results
20	Driving Simulation Conference Europe 2025 VR	September 2025	TBD	DLR, REN, RWTH (IKA)	Human-in-the-loop study plans and results, Scenario generation for simulators
21	VDI Conference "Vehicle Safety"	November 2025	Berlin, Germany	VUFO	TBD

22	carhs ADAS Experience	September 2025	Germany	VUFO	TBD
23	Transport Research Board Automated Road Transportation Symposium (TRB ARTS)	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	TBD	IDIADA, PAVE	Main project results, Capacity building programme presentation
24	ADAS & Autonomous Vehicle Technology Expo & Conference	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	TBD	IDIADA	Main project results
25	EU Conference on Results from Road Transport Research (RTR)	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	TBD	IDIADA	Main project results
26	Urban Mobility Days	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	TBD	IDIADA	Main project results
27	Open Auto Drive Forum	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	TBD	IDIADA	Main project results
28	TRA	May 18-21, 2026	Budapest, Hungary	CLEPA, ICCS, ERTICO, MOSAIC FACTOR SL	TBD
29	ARTS 2026	July 2026	USA	PAVE Europe	Presentation on capacity building programmes
30	Driving Simulation Conference Europe 2026 VR	2026 (Date TBD)	TBD	DLR	Human-In-The-Loop Study Plans & Results
31	ESV 2026	2026	Canada	VUFO	TBD
32	EARPA Future of Road Mobility Forum	2026	TBD	IDIADA	Main project results
33	crash.tech 2026	March 2026	Ingolstadt / Germany	VUFO	TBD

Table 4 Key conferences and events for SYNERGIES

3.2.5.3 Journal publications and conference proceedings

Moreover, other than using the events, SYNERGIES will make or publish its results in the form of articles in reviewed scholarly journals, proceedings of the conferences, and appropriate magazines. Such publications will appeal to the scientific community, industrialists and policy makers to improve the use of the projects common results in various fields.

Publication No.	Targeted Journals / Conferences	Place/Date	Topic	Partners Involved
1	IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems	Open	Advanced Version of Trajectory and Scenario Reconstruction, focus on method and mathematical advances	VIF, ICCS
2	ITS World Congress	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Main project results	IDIADA, ICCS and others TBD
3	CVF (ICCV, CVPR, WACV), DSC Europe, or similar	TBD	Synthetization of realistic scenarios	RISE
4	ITS European Congress	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Main project results	IDIADA
5	IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transport Systems (ITSC)	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Main project results	RWTH (IKA), CEESAR, IDIADA
6	SIA Vision ADAS		Accident in ADScene: a specific survey on AD L2+ functions	REN, CEESAR
7	IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Main project results	CEESAR, IDIADA, RWTH (IKA), VIF
8	FMAS 2025	t.b.a.	Criticality analysis for scenario identification	DLR
9	Driving Simulation Conference Europe 2025 VR	t.b.a.	Human-In-The-Loop Study Plans & Results from T5.4	DLR, RWTH (IKA)
10	IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transport Systems (ITSC)	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Results WP4 activities (T4.4)	VICOM
11	Transport Research Arena (TRA)	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Project Results	CLEPA, IDIADA
12	FISITA Technology of Mobility Conference	Annual (expected 2025, 2026, 2027)	Main project results	IDIADA

13	IEEE IV, IEEE ITSC, Open Journal of ITS, or similar	TBD	Work on data collection and/or generative AI	TBD
14	MDPI Sensors or IEEE Journal	TBD	New trained sensor models respectively its advances	VIF

Table 5 Journal publications and conference proceedings

3.2.5.4 Clustering Activities and Collaboration

The SYNERGIES will, moreover connect with relevant other projects in order to maximize its impact as well as enhance knowledge exchange within the CCAM community. Similar consortium activities will consist of joint workshops, publications and networking with the projects FAME, Hi-Drive, SUNRISE among other activities. In respect to met projects, SYNERGIES will adjust validation processes, develop compatible scenario databases, and provide bodies like ISO, SAE, ASAM, UNECE and Euro NCAP with information they were looking for.

Moreover, SYNERGIES will make trilateral meetings as well as collaboration agreements with JARI for working on projects like Sakura and with the Transportation Research Board (US) reinforcing internationalisation of such cooperation. The project will also closely coordinate with activities supported by the European Data Strategy Initiative to build a federated and cross-interoperable scenario dataspace which conforms to the data sharing policies within Europe.

These clustering activities will ensure that SYNERGIES will be leading in the development of the CCAM and promote sharing of knowledge as well as standardization in several sectors and areas.

Collaboration No.	Relevant Organization/Project	Type of Activity	Date	Place
1	Hi-Drive and SUNRISE Projects	Knowledge sharing, harmonization of validation	2024-2026	Europe
2	JARI (Sakura Project)	Cooperation during project execution	TBD	Japan, Europe
3	KATRI – South Korea	Cooperation during project execution	TBD	South Korea, Europe
4	SUNRISE, SINFONICA, FAME, CONNECT Projects	Workshop	2025	TBD
5	Transport Canada-EU	Cooperation during project execution	TBD	Canada, Europe

6	AVSC, VTTI - US	Cooperation during project execution	TBD	US, Europe
7	CARRS-Q - Australia	Cooperation during project execution	TBD	Australia, Europe
8	EU - Chips-JU (Edge-AI Trust Project)	We will explore synergies between edge computing and scenario-based testing	TBD	TBD
9	EARPA (European Automotive Research Partners Association)	Presentation	TBD	TBD
10	CDC (Cluster Digital de Catalunya)	Talk	TBD	Barcelona (Spain)
11	In-MOVE by Railgroup	Talk	TBD	Barcelona (Spain)
12	UN GRVA Scenario workshop	Regulation Promote SYNERGIES as the path to interoperability between existing SCDB and as a SCBD	TBD	TBD
13	French Ministry of Transport	Regulation	December, 2024	Paris
14	Transportation Research Board (US)	Collaborative workshops on CCAM	2025	US, Europe
15	European Data Strategy Initiatives	Creating interoperable scenario dataspace	2024-2026	Europe
16	ISO, SAE, ASAM, UNECE, Euro NCAP	Participation in standardization discussions	2024-2026	Global
17	FAME	Joint workshops, project alignment	2025	TBD
18	Various CCAM Projects	Joint publications and events	2024-2026	TBD

19	ATHENA	Cooperation with EU-funded project	TBD	TBD
20	GaiaX 4 PLC-AAD	Technical input into the SYNERGIES project, OS+Specifications	Cont. until Q1/25	online
21	asc(s e.V.	Proposal: Associated Partnership to leverage association for dissemination through various events like e.g. Simpulse Days	asap	Next Steering board meeting
22	ASAM e.V.	Exchange via participation in standardization projects (especially ASAM OpenX Simulation Standards)	Cont.	Online / on-site project meetings

Table 6 Clustering activities and collaboration in SYNERGIES

3.2.6 Dissemination roadmap

This roadmap of dissemination will correspond to the important progress of the project so that activities of communication will follow essential stages and outcomes in the project.

Phase	Focus	Key Metrics for Success
Phase 1 (M01-M08)	Creating initial project awareness and building anticipation.	Media engagement, initial web traffic metrics, participation in foundational conferences.
Phase 2 (M09-M24)	Disseminating preliminary findings and fostering deeper engagement with technical stakeholders.	Publication citations, feedback from conference presentations, participation in collaborative workshops.
Phase 3 (M25-M36)	Showcasing final results and driving towards exploitation.	Securing buy-in from industry and policymakers, invitations to contribute to standardization efforts, integration into real-world applications.

Table 7 Dissemination roadmap

3.2.7 KPIs

Dissemination activities will be rigorously assessed through a data-driven approach. Metrics will not only track volume but also the quality of engagement and influence on key audiences.

- **Conference participation:** The target will be 8 conferences per year that will not be measured in terms of presence only but also in presence and partnerships formed after all these interactions.

- **Scientific publications:** In addition to the 20 papers focus, bibliometrics and the article citations, impact of the journal and any publications on the research and practice will also be taken into consideration.
- **Webinars:** Educate wider society about CCAM safety, online webinar will be conducted along with an online platform to crowd source scenarios from general public. Materials to train engineers in the whole process of "scenario generation" from processed data.
- **Summer School:** Building on the experience from Hi-Drive.

Tools/Channels	Key Performance Indicator	Target value			
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
Conferences	Conference Participation: Number	>8	>8	>8	>24
Publications	Scientific publications (journal & conference proceedings): Number	>1	>8	>11	>20
Webinars	Number		>2	>2	>4
Summer School	Number		>1		>1

Table 8 Dissemination KPIs in SYNERGIES

3.2.8 Conclusion

The dissemination plan for SYNERGIES is a well thought out document that outlines how best to promote the results of the project on the connected, cooperative and automated mobility (CCAM) domain. To achieve its objectives, SYNERGIES will capitalize on a variety of means of dissemination which include but are not limited to activities such as conferences, publishing, workshops and the usage of various digital media.

One important part of the plan is the focus on various cluster and collaboration activities. In cooperation with Hi-Drive and SUNRISE projects and global cooperation like the JARI Sakura Project as well as participating in standards bodies like ISO, SAE, ASAM and Euro NCAP, SYNERGIES will enhance its developments towards the world and encourage progress. These activities are even more supported by the participation of SYNERGIES in important conferences and other events where it will be able to present what has been achieved and collect feedback.

The approach to dissemination for the project goes beyond simple exposure onto engagement that drives on acceptance, compliance and potential future collaboration. Through the strategic action of evolving its dissemination channels as the project progresses, SYNERGIES is well positioned to exercise meaningful impact on the CCAM ecosystem that ensures that its innovations integrate to safer, efficient and sustainable mobility systems.

3.3 Dissemination of SYNERGIES through standardization (T10.3)

Partners of this task will jointly work on a Whitepaper giving an overview on used standards and on parts of the project's approach, currently not covered by a standard. For the uncovered parts an outline for potential standardization will be drafted to help initiating further standardization based on projects outcomes.

The overall **standardization concept** is planned as follows:

- The technical WPs (2,3,4,5,6 and maybe 7 and 8) will make technical developments.
- This task will identify and select which of those technical developments are suitable for introduction for new standards or standard "renewal" and prepare such technical content in a digestible way for the standardization bodies (i.e., drafts, standard structure, objective, scope, etc.)
- The task will follow closely the development of related standards such as ISO/DIS 34504, ASAM, ISO/PAS 8800, etc., and establish conversations for contribution.
- T9.2 should reach out to the standardization bodies and present the material generated (i.e., PowerPoint, Whitepaper).

Task plan:

- Create **list with known and used standards** in the domains of technical WPs
 - T10.3 participants to create draft list
 - Distribute to WP leaders, and get feedback
 - Update yearly (M1-M6, M12-M18, M24-M30)
 - **Goal: to ensure SYNERGIES is aligned with international standards in the field**
- Create **list with standards under development** in the domains of technical WPs
 - T10.3 participants to create draft list
 - Distribute to WP leaders, and get feedback
 - Update yearly (M1-M6, M12-M18, M24-M30)
 - **Goal: to identify opportunities for SYNERGIES partners to participate in ongoing standard development projects or to pre-align**
- Monitor SYNERGIES technical developments to **identify potential gaps** of current standardization landscape
 - WP leaders to provide list of technical developments
 - T10.3 participants to evaluate the need for standardization (+ workshops with international cooperation in T9.3)
 - Draft an outline for potential standardization
 - **Goal: to report what parts of SYNERGIES are not covered by existing or under-development standards**
- Prepare deliverable (**Whitepaper and conclusions**) (M30 – M36)

Rules from the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement regarding standardization:

- If results are incorporated in a standard, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority or unless it is impossible) **ask the standardization body to include the funding statement** in (information related to) the standard.
- The Party who wishes to incorporate their **own Results** into an industry standard will **inform all other Parties in writing**. The information must include details about the standardization organization and purpose in addition to the content. **Incorporating joint owned Results** (...) into an industry standard **requires the consent of all Parties involved** in the affected work Result. Consent must not be unreasonably withheld or delayed. The

concerned Party is obliged to respond within two (2) months from the receipt of the request, otherwise, after this period, consent shall be deemed given.

3.4 Dissemination of SYNERGIES through education and training (T10.4)

The successful dissemination of the Synergies project hinges **on comprehensive education and training initiatives** designed to onboard new users, empower engineers, and engage the wider society. The multifaceted approach taken will ensure the project's tools, methodologies, and **results are accessible and valuable to a broad audience**.

One of the key elements in the dissemination strategy is the **effective onboarding of new users to the SYNERGIES Platform and tools**. This involves detailed training sessions that guide users on how to navigate and utilize the scenario dataspace and the various tools available. This aspect of the task is **closely linked to Work Package 7 (WP7)**, which aims to produce a comprehensive user handbook. The user handbook will serve as an essential resource, providing step-by-step instructions, best practices, and troubleshooting tips to help users quickly become proficient in using the platform.

To ensure that engineers can fully leverage the SYNERGIES environment, **specialized training materials are being developed**. These materials **focus on the entire process of "scenario generation"** from processed data, although they also cover other parts of the toolchain. By providing detailed guidance on how to create and manage scenarios, the training materials aim to enhance engineers' capabilities and streamline their workflows.

These training materials will be valorised during live events such as **webinars** and potentially **"summer schools."** Drawing on experience from similar events organized in the Hi-Drive project, these sessions will offer **hands-on training and real-time interaction with experts**. Participants will have the opportunity to ask questions, share experiences, and gain insights that can only be obtained through direct engagement with trainers and peers. Two webinars are planned, one in year 2 and one in year 3. It is planned to organise a 'summer school' on the third year of the project.

In addition to training engineers and new users, the SYNERGIES project is committed to educating the wider society about Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) safety. To this end, an **online webinar** will be conducted to raise awareness and disseminate crucial safety information. This webinar will be complemented by an online platform designed to crowdsource scenarios from the general public. By **involving the public in the scenario generation process**, the project not only educates but also empowers individuals to contribute to the safety and development of CCAM technologies.

A cornerstone of the dissemination strategy is the creation of **openly available documentation and training materials** based on the project's demonstrations. This documentation will include recorded and processed data from the project, providing users with practical examples and case studies. By making these resources freely accessible, the SYNERGIES project aims to **extend its impact beyond its immediate participants**, enabling external users to apply the project's results in their own contexts.

To further maximize the impact of the project, parts of the project's demonstration artefacts will be incorporated into the documentation and training materials. These artefacts, which include recorded and processed data, will serve as valuable resources for both training and reference. By including real-world examples and data, the documentation and training materials will provide users with a deeper understanding of the project's methodologies and outcomes, fostering greater adoption and implementation of the SYNERGIES platform.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This document sets out the project's dissemination and communication plan, as well as its guidelines and opportunities.

The SYNERGIES plan will be updated annually (month 12 and month 24) as part of the periodic reporting. In addition, a final report will be released in M36.

Recurrent actions to take include the update of the project website and social media accounts, and the update of the project templates, as outlined in Chapter 3. Further actions include the constant publications of news on SYNERGIES's website and social media posts, as well as the project newsletters, and advertising the participation of partners in relevant meetings. A quarterly analysis of social media statistics and a quarterly assessment of cooperation tools will also provide direct measures of the successful engagement of the stakeholder community.

The communication and dissemination strategy has identified and described the target groups for dissemination and communication activities and highlighted how and through which communication and dissemination channels they will be reached. The related plan describes the main dissemination tools, which will be fundamental for outreach activities. The guidelines and KPIs highlighted in this document will allow to achieve and go beyond the project's communication and dissemination goals.

An initial overview about the planned implementation of the standardization, education, and training activities has been provided.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] European IPR Helpdesk: "Fact Sheet - The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020", July 2015
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- [3] European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Dissemination and exploitation strategy for Horizon Europe – Towards an integrated dissemination & exploitation ecosystem, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/650016>
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A. SYNERGIES DISSEMINATION PROCEDURE

Description and purpose

The participation of any partner in an event, the publication or presentation of work done within the framework of SYNERGIES, or the performance of any other dissemination activity related to the project must be approved beforehand by the SYNERGIES Consortium.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally to:

- Produce high-quality SYNERGIES publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Efficiently monitor, record, and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- Secure the brand identity of the project and ensure EC (European Commission)/rules are followed.

The **WP10 Leader (VIF)** and the **Task 10.2 Leader (ICCS)** are responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. All partners are encouraged to contribute efficiently to the dissemination of the project.

Step-by-step procedure

Before any dissemination activity related to the SYNERGIES project, the initiator of the activity should:

STEP 1: Notify the **Task 10.2 Leader** dimitris.maragkos@iccs.gr (ICCS) at least 15 working days³ in advance about the intention to participate in a dissemination activity. When it comes to scientific publications prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the coordinator **IDIADA** and **T10.2 leader** at least 30 calendar days before the publication⁴. The following details should be shared in all cases:

- a) Details of the activity (date of event, title of activity, title of publication audience, etc.),
- b) The specific role in the activity (presenter, organizer, speaker, etc.), and
- c) A short description (up to 150 words) of the activity and how it is related to SYNERGIES.

STEP 2: Register the activity in the applicable tab on the [Dissemination Register](#), specifying all details regarding the activity as indicated in each column of the file.

STEP 3: If applicable, store the relevant material (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release, etc.) in the WP10 Dissemination folder on **SharePoint** under the related sub-folder (Conference participation, presentation ,poster etc).

STEP 4: The **Task 10.2 Leader** has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification, or rejection. Regarding Scientific Publications the Coordinator will distribute the publication to all partners.

³ Article 17.4 of the GA

⁴ Article 9.4.1.1 of the CA

STEP 5: Any Consortium member may raise a modification or rejection request along with comments, which should be sent to the **Task 10.2 Leader** within 15 days. No response is considered as approval. When it comes to a scientific publication any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 20 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

STEP 6: The **Task 10.2 Leader** informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

In case of:

- **Approval:** The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity.
- **Conflict/Objection:** Any Consortium member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example, in cases of risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The objection must include clear reasoning and a precise request for necessary modifications to make the dissemination acceptable. The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the Task 10.2 Leader, and the involved partners.

Dissemination activities report

Within ten working days after the realization of the dissemination activity, the partner must provide the **Task 10.2 Leader** with the filled dissemination report ([available on SharePoint](#)) and the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster, etc.). It is also appreciated if the lead partner of every dissemination activity provides the **WP10 Leader** and **Task 10.2 Leader** with some photos of the event participation. Partners should complete all fields briefly and clearly, avoiding abbreviations. The filled report, along with all received material, will be archived by ICCS to the Dissemination Activity Inventory on **SharePoint**.

EU acknowledgment

All recipients of EU funds are legally obliged to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This obligation, specified under Article 17 of the grant agreement for Horizon Europe projects, requires all beneficiaries to acknowledge the support from the European Union on all communication materials. **The European Union emblem and the funding statement (available on SharePoint and below) must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels, and other communication products.**

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**Funded by
the European Union**

B. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITY REPORT

The dissemination activities report should be filled in by the leading partner of every realised dissemination activity. The purpose of this report is to provide the necessary information to the WP10 Leader and Task 10.2 Leader for publishing the activity to the SYNERGIES website and for reporting to the European Commission.

There are three report tables in this document:

- a) A report in case of an event (e.g., project event, conference, exhibition, etc.);
- b) A report in case of a scientific publication (e.g., conference papers, journals/magazines, book chapter, etc.);
- c) A report in case of any other dissemination activity related to SYNERGIES.

Please fill in the applicable report table and **send the document to the Task 10.2 Leader (Dimitris Maragkos, ICCS) : Dimitris.maragkos@iccs.gr** along with any presented material (full paper, article, poster, presentation etc.), also indicating whether the WP10 team has the permission to publicise this material (e.g., on the website, on zenodo, etc.).

In case of Events (i.e. Project Events, Conference Presentations, Exhibitions etc.)	
Title of event / place & date of realisation:	
Type of Event:	Conference, Workshop, educational training etc.
Title of presentation:	
Type of presentation:	poster presentation, paper presentation, demo presentation, oral presentation...
Relevance to SYNERGIES:	Please specify: WPx work, concept description etc.
Author(s)/ Presenter(s):	Name (company)
Other activities (if any)	i.e. distribution of promotional material, bilateral discussions etc.
Type of audience addressed (event/meeting)	Scientific community (higher education, research)
	Industry
	Civil society
	Policy makers / Public authorities
	Media
	Other: please specify

In case of an Event:	NATIONAL: hosting country: [] Number of attendees: []
	INTERNATIONAL: hosting country: [] addressed countries: [] Number of overall attendees: [] Size of audience addressed by the performed activity: []
	Liaison with relevant actors: no, yes: partners, projects, initiatives, shared session? []. Any feedback received? no, yes: Please specify.
In case of a meeting:	LOCAL: Number of attendees: []
	NATIONAL: hosting country: [] Number of attendees: []
	INTERNATIONAL: addressed countries: [] Number of attendees: []
	Main purpose of the meeting: [] / Relevance to SYNERGIES []
	Related contacts made: [] / Feedback received: []
Do you foresee further involvement of the actors you met with? []	

Table 9 Events reporting

In case of Scientific Publications (Conference papers, journals / magazines, book chapter etc.)	
Type of publication	journal article, conference paper, book chapter etc.
Main Author (name, organisation)	[]
Title of publication:	[]
Relevance to SYNERGIES:	Please specify: WPx work, concept description etc.
Other Authors:	[]
In case of a journal/magazine article:	Title of journal or magazine: []
	Volume, page: []
	Editor / Publisher: []
	ISSN: []

In case of a Conference paper:	Title of proceedings	<input type="text"/>
	Editor/publisher:	<input type="text"/>
In case of a book publication:	Title of book:	<input type="text"/>
	Title of Chapter:	<input type="text"/>
	Editor / Publisher:	<input type="text"/>
	Pages:	<input type="text"/>
	ISBN:	<input type="text"/>
For all publications:	Date of publication:	<input type="text"/>
	URL (if available)	<input type="text"/>
	DOI number	<input type="text"/>
	Open access to publication?	no yes: (way to get it)
	Additional info:	<input type="text"/>

Table 10 Scientific publications reporting

Other activities	
Type of activity:	i.e. video presentation, event organisation, website announcement, press briefings, interviews etc.
Title:	<input type="text"/>
Occasion:	Name of Event/ publication etc.
URL:	<input type="text"/>
Relevance to SYNERGIES:	<input type="text"/>
Partners Involved:	<input type="text"/>
Short description:	<input type="text"/>
Other Comments:	<input type="text"/>

Table 11 Other activities reporting

C. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
AD	Automated Driving
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASAM	Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
BSI	British Standards Institution
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
Euro NCAP	European New Car Assessment Programme
GA	Grant Agreement
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PCA	Project Consortium Agreement
ROI	Return of Investment
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SUNRISE	Safety Assurance Framework for Connected and Automated Mobility Systems
SYNERGIES	Real and Synthetic Scenarios Generated for the Development, Training, Virtual Testing and Validation Of CCAM Systems
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
WP	Work Package